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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE
OF CONTRACEPTIVES IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE
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Abstract:

Contraceptive methods in family planning were a big innovation for control of fast-growing population. The world population has been reached to a set target in the developed world. However, Pakistan, which is the 6th populous country of world and 4th in Asia, still face problem with the control of fast-growing population. The population of Pakistan will double to 260 million by the year 2035. Marriage at young age, increasing fertility rate, increasing poverty, unintended pregnancy, unsafe abortion and sexually transmitted diseases continue to be major health problem and are indicators for an increasing need for modern methods of contraceptive utilization in Pakistan. This was a descriptive correctional study conducted to assess contraceptive knowledge, attitude and practices in Faisal Abad City from 1 May 2018 to 10 Jun 2018. Total 420 women of reproductive age (20 – 49) participated in the survey. Out of 420, 316 women gave response to questions. Data was collected from the population of Faisal Abad by self-structured questionnaire. For data analysis, SPSS version 21 has been used. Results were compiled and then compared with international and national literature. Mostly married women with children (92.7%) had good knowledge of contraceptives. Knowledge of women about different types of contraceptive was 74.1%. Among the sampled population attitude was checked by five-point Likert scale. Most married women were practicing condom (21.1) and mini progesterone pills (20.3%) respectively. Married women (31.6%) were practicing more than one contraceptive method. The main reason behind the use of contraceptives was birth spacing (37%). Most of the women (67%) were agreed that People do not use contraceptives due to lack of knowledge/ partner disapproval/ religion. The practice was high in women of age (36-45) but low in women of age (18-25), which was due the illiteracy. By increasing the educational status of women, we can improve the practice of contraception.

Key Words: Knowledge, contraceptives, abortion, fertility, illiteracy**Corresponding author:****Dr. Mehrina Abbas,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Unintended pregnancy, safe abortion and sexually transmitted diseases including HIV infection continue to be a major reproductive health problem globally. The hungry and impoverished people of underdeveloped countries are desperate for the chance to improve their own lives and to provide a better existence for their children. (Farzana Aamir, 2014)

The world population has been stabilized in the developed world but Pakistan is the seventh most populous country in the world and fourth in Asia with a population 130.6 million in 1998, with growth rate of 2.45%. The population of Pakistan will double to 260 million by the year 2035. (Farzana Aamir, 2014) Moreover, according to the Population Reference Bureau 2005; the estimated population of Pakistan is 162.4 million and is expected to be 295 million in the year 2050. (2015) And it is also difficult for the state to provide basic human facilities to its people i.e. food, clothing, housing, health and education. (Farzana Aamir, 2014)

Inclusion of modern contraceptive methods in family planning was a big innovation for control of fast-growing population. Family planning has become very important for the achievement of Minimum Development Goal (MDG) (Malik, 2015, Najafi-Sharjabad et al., 2013). It is one of the four pillars, which are antenatal care, safe delivery and postnatal care and are introduced in 1981 by the safe motherhood initiative to reduce maternal mortality. It provides individuals a decision making power to attain their desired number of children and spacing of their childbirth. (Najafi-Sharjabad et al., 2013)

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: The study was performed to assess contraceptive knowledge, attitude and practices. A descriptive cross-sectional study was performed in Faisal Abad City. Data was collected from the population of Faisal Abad by self-structured questionnaire. Which was then compiled, and results was made through this data.

Study setting: The area of study is Faisal Abad City of the province Punjab, Pakistan. The population of Faisal Abad is 3.029 million (1998). In addition, all the women were included in the study. Data was collected through all the women of Faisal Abad, which were representing the Faisal Abad city of province Punjab.

OBJECTIVES:

General Objective: Aim of this study is to evaluate the Knowledge, attitude and practice about contraceptives in young women of reproductive age.

Specific Objective:

- To assess the awareness of the young women who have reached their reproductive age.
- To assess their attitude about using contraceptives.
- To evaluate the barriers of not using contraceptives.
- To assess their level of practice of using contraceptive in their daily routine.

Study Population: Study was performed on the population of Faisal Abad and the population of Faisal Abad city is 3.029 million (1998). The population is enough to collect the data, which was, represent that how much the women are aware from the modern contraceptive method and their use in Faisal Abad City.

Sample Size: Group of individuals involve in the study is sample size. The sample size of population of Faisal Abad was 420. 420 women of the reproductive age will be involved in the study and data was collected from them

Sampling Procedure: Simple random sampling was done to get the sample size of population, which was required for collecting the data, and represented all the population of Faisal Abad City.

Inclusion criteria: The data will be collected only from the women. Women of the reproductive age (15-49) years was included in the study. All of them should live in Faisal Abad.

Exclusion criteria: Women of the age of less than 15 and more than 40 years will be excluded from the study.

Data Collection: The quantitative study was performed on the population of Faisal Abad. Women of reproductive age were selected to collect the data. Data was collected by a specially designed closed ended questionnaire. Total 420 married women of reproductive age group (15 – 49yrs) filled questionnaire, which includes age, parity, socioeconomic status, educational level. Information was also gathered about knowledge, attitude, practices and barriers to the utilization of different types of contraceptive methods. Questionnaire also has the demographic data of the respondent.

Data collection tool: After extensive literature review, a self-administered questionnaire was designed to conduct this study. The questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts which were composed of e senior academic researchers and was updated according to their recommendations.

For knowledge statements, respondents were asked to choose “Yes” or “No” options.

Correct answer (yes) was scored 1, while incorrect answer (no) was scored 0.

A five-point Likert scale was used for perception and attitude statements (strongly agree=5, agree=4, neutral=3, disagree=2 and strongly disagree=1).

Data Analysis: The SPSS Version 20 statistical package was used for data entry and analysis. The validity of the data collected was done by double entry and by random checks for errors. Relevant frequency

distributions tables and summary measures were generated. The Chi-square test was used to demonstrate relationships between categorical variables, and the level of significance will set at P-values # 0.05, at the confidence interval of 95%, for all inferential analysis. Chi-square tests of independence were used to determine differences in the characteristics of members of different age. Descriptive statistics were used to compare knowledge and attitudes towards the use of contraceptive methods. Mean, median and standard deviation was derived by SPSS of different parameters.

RESULTS:

Sr. No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Age	18-25 years	63	19%
		26-23 years	109	34.50%
		36-45 years	73	23%
		>45 years	71	22.50%
2	Marital status	Married	92	29%
		Widowed	11	3.50%
		Divorced	12	3.80%
		Married with children	200	63.30%
3	Academic status	Illiterate	58	18.40%
		Primary	21	6.60%
		Secondary	74	23.40%
		Higher secondary	62	19.60%
		Graduate	75	23.70%
4	Occupational status	Post graduate	24	7.60%
		House wife	185	58.50%
		Employ	44	13.90%
		Self-employed	8	25.30%
5	Household income	Students	7	2.20%
		<13,000	49	15.50%
		13,000-20,000	73	23.10%
		21,000-30,000	106	33.50%
6	Husband education	>30,000	88	27.80%
		Illiterate	46	14.60%
		Primary	22	17.00%
		Secondary	37	11.70%
		Higher secondary	54	17.10%
		Graduate	100	31.60%
		Post graduate	57	18.00%
7	No. of living children	None	23	7.30%
		1	35	11.10%
		Currently pregnant	22	7.00%
		More than 1	236	74.70%

The total frequency of all the variables of socio-demographic data is 316 and the output frequency of every variable is given in above table.

The percentage of the entire variable is given in table 1.

Study was performed on the population of Faisal Abad to access the knowledge attitude and practice of contraceptive use among women. Questionnaire was formed which is then used to collect the data. Total sample size for this research was 420 and 316 women were responded the questions. Data was collected and

results were formed on SPSS file. Women's of different age groups were responded to the question. Data revealed that 19% of the women were at the age of 18-25 years. 34.5% of the women were at the age of 26-23 years. 23% of the women were at the age of 36-45 years. And more than 45 years of age were 22.5%. Further socio-demographic data shows that 18.4% of the women were illiterate, 17.6% were at the primary education level, 11.7% were at the secondary level of education, 19.6% were at higher secondary level of education, 31.6% were at graduated and 7.6% women were at post graduate level of education.

Table 2: Knowledge

Sr. No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Have you ever heard about contraceptives?	293	92.7%
2	Do you have information about contraceptive use patterns?	207	65.5%
3	Do you think contraceptives are a kind of abortion method?	16	5.1%
4	Do you think contraceptives are effective from preventive pregnancy?	308	97.5%
5	Are you familiar with different types of contraceptive i.e. oral contraceptive?	234	74.5%
6	Do you think contraceptive is ethical?	251	79.4%
7	Do you think contraceptives easily available in market?	312	98.7%

The total frequency of all the variable of knowledge is 316 and all frequency is out of 316 is given in above table.

The output percentage of all the variables of knowledge questions are given in above table.

Studies show that 92.7% of all the women's that are involved in the study have knowledge about the contraceptives. 65.5% of the women's have knowledge

about the use pattern of the contraceptives. 5.1% women think that contraceptive use is a type of abortion method. 97.5% of women have knowledge that contraceptives are used to avoid pregnancy. 74.5% of women have knowledge about the different type of the contraceptives e. g oral contraceptives. 79.4% women think that the use of contraceptive is ethical. Studies further revealed that 98.7% have easy approach to contraceptives in the market and they think that contraceptives are easily available in the market.

Table 3. Attitude

Sr. No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Contraceptives should be used only whenever needed.	236	74.7%
2	Contraceptives should be used only, if its benefits are ensured.	247	78.2%
3	Contraceptives are beneficial in family planning.	239	75.6%
4	Women should suggest their partner to use contraceptive.	198	62.7%
5	People use contraceptives for birth control.	211	66.8%
6	People don't use contraceptives due to lack of knowledge/ partner disapproval/ religion.	205	64.9%
7	The use of contraceptive useful measure in decreasing health risk.	141	44.6%
8	Contraceptives should be widely advertised by media.	76	24.1%
9	Mother should discuss about contraceptive with their daughter.	249	78.8%

The total frequency of all the variable is 316 and the output frequency of all the variables are given in above table.

The output percentage of all the variables is given in above table.

Studies show that most of the women think that contraceptives should be used when they needed. 74.4% think that contraceptives should be used when they needed. 78.3% think that the contraceptives should be used if its benefits are ensured. 75.6% think

that contraceptives are beneficial for family planning. 62.7% women suggest their partner to use contraceptives. 66.8% of women think people use contraceptives for birth control. 64.9% of the women think that people don't use contraceptives due to lack of knowledge, Partner disapproval or religion. 44.6% of the women think that use of contraceptive is useful in decreasing health risk. 24.1% think that contraceptives should be widely advertised on media. 78.8% women think that they should discuss about contraceptives to their daughters.

Table4 Practice

Sr. No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Have you ever used contraceptive?	212	67.1%
2	The decision about the contraceptive is taken by you?	138	43.7%
3	Do you find any difficulty in using contraceptive?	31	9.8%
4	Have you experienced any ADR by the use of contraceptive?	68	21.5%
5	Have you ever advised your close contacts to use contraceptives for family planning?	249	78.8%

The total frequency of all the variables of above table is 316 and output frequency of each variable is given in the table.

DISCUSSION:

This study was conducted to evaluate the current contraceptive attitude, knowledge and practice in women of reproductive age belonging to 'Faisal Abad' which is the 3 most populous city of Pakistan. Moreover, to access the factors which are barriers for not using contraceptives? Total 420 women participated in the survey. However, out of 420 women 316 women gave response to our questions. Intensive literature review showed that the awareness about contraceptive among women is high but the practice is still low due to illiteracy. A study conducted for assessment of knowledge, practices and barriers in family planning services in Korangi industrial area Karachi showed that 74% females was illiterate & majority of them belongs to low socioeconomic class, the main reason behind hindrances in practice in this area was illiteracy, and low socioeconomic status. (Farzana Aamir, 2014) Another study conducted to investigate the knowledge, attitude and practices of contraception in women of reproductive age in Liaquat Memorial Hospital, Kohat, Pakistan showed that Frequency of contraceptive use is low despite high level of awareness. The main factors were Desire for larger family, pressure from husband, religious concerns and fear of side effects. (Jabeen et al., 2012) This study also showed that 81.6% declared family planning as prohibited in the religion. A study conducted to assess contraceptive knowledge, practices, availability and

accessibility of family planning services and reasons for non-utilization of family planning services in interior of Sindh province, Pakistan also showed that the current contraceptive practices are not at the expected levels and the main reason behind this was fear of side effects. (Bibi et al., 2008) All these studies showed that factors behind not using contraceptives are husband disapproval, in-laws pressure, religious concerns and fear of side effects. In addition, the reason behind all these factors was illiteracy. According to Pakistan Demographic and Health survey (2012-13), Fertility rate is directly proportional to mother's education; women with higher education have 2.5 children while women with no education have 4.4 children. The majority (57%) of married Pakistani women and 29% of married men age 15-49 have no education. Only 16% of women and 21% of men have only achieved primary education. One in five women and one in three men have achieved higher education. This shows that both women and men must achieve higher education. According to this survey, modern contraceptive use can increase with education. (Demographic, 2015) Literature review also showed that Pakistan is the sixth most populous country in world, which is still facing the problem of fast growing population. According to the "Population Reference Bureau 2015", the estimated population of Pakistan is 199 million and is expected to be 344 million in the 2050 a result that does not meet the target of 2015 (2015). (2015) This increase in population is causing difficulty for the country to provide basic human facilities like food, clothing, housing, health and education. Unsafe abortion increase

mortality and morbidity rates may be due to low use of modern long-term contraceptive methods.

The findings of our study indicate that majority of women were aware of contraceptive methods. Most of the women knew about the modern contraceptive's methods. This study also found positive attitude regarding the use of contraceptive methods. Majority of women agreed that contraceptives are beneficial in family planning; people use contraceptives for birth control and the use of contraceptives is useful measure in decreasing health risks. Most of the women strongly agreed that contraceptives should be used only whenever needed; contraceptives should be used only if its benefits are ensured and people do not use contraceptives due to lack of knowledge/ partner disapproval/ religious believes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

The objective of our study was to obtain knowledge; attitude and practice of contraceptive methods in married women of reproductive age. This study also conducted to evaluate the reasons behind not using contraceptives. In our study, the level of practice increased with increasing age. The main reason of practicing of contraceptive was birth spacing and completed family. In this survey majority of women said that they did not experience any ADR by the use of contraceptives, and they did not find any difficulty in using contraceptives. Moreover, most of the women with higher age were practicing more than one method of contraception. The knowledge about contraceptives among women was high. Women also strongly agreed that contraceptives are beneficial in family planning; contraceptives should be used only when its benefits are ensured. Women also agreed that people do not use contraceptives due to lack of knowledge/ partner disapproval/ religion.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdul-hadi, Abass, Aiyenigba, Oseni, Odafe, Chabikuli, Ibrahim, Hamelmann & Ladipo 2013. The effectiveness of community-based distribution of injectable contraceptives using community health extension workers in Gombe State, Northern Nigeria. *African journal of reproductive health*, 17, 80-88.
2. Akhtar, Khan, Ahmad & Hussain 2011. FAMILY PLANNING METHODS AND GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF CHILDREN IN A DEFINED RURAL COMMUNITY OF PESHAWAR. *Journal of Postgraduate Medical Institute (Peshawar-Pakistan)*, 25.
3. Ayub, Kibria & Khan 2015. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Contraceptive use in Married Women of Peshawar. *Journal of Dow University of Health Sciences*, 9.
4. Azmat 2011. Mobilizing male opinion leaders' support for family planning to improve maternal health: a theory-based qualitative study from Pakistan. *Journal of multidisciplinary healthcare*, 4, 421-431.
5. Bibi, Memon, Memon & Bibi 2008. Contraceptive knowledge and practices in two districts of Sindh, Pakistan: a hospital based study. *Age (years)*, 15, 21-30.
6. Carton & Agha 2011. Changes in contraceptive use and method mix in Pakistan: 1990-91 to 2006-07. *Health policy and planning*, czr022.
7. Gizaw & Regassa 2011. Family planning service utilization in Mojo town, Ethiopia: A population based study. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning*, 4, 355.
8. Khan, Hashmani, Ahmed, Khan, Ahmed, Syed & Qazi 2015. Quantitatively evaluating the effect of social barriers: a case-control study of family members' opposition and women's intention to use contraception in Pakistan. *Emerging themes in epidemiology*, 12, 1.